

CEMENT BASED NANOCOMPOSITES WITH SELF-DIAGNOSTIC CHARACTERISTICS

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the development of cement based nanocomposites with self-diagnostic characteristics by reinforcing the cementitious matrix with exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets (xGnPs). The piezoresistive response of the developed cement-based nanocomposites was assessed by monitoring their electrical resistance change as a function of the applied mechanical stress (a) under monotonic compression and (b) compressive loading-unloading in the elastic region (maximum stress applied was 10 MPa). The results were compared with the respective results from reference samples (without reinforcement). The non-reinforced samples didn't exhibit piezoresistive behaviour, while the incorporation of the xGnPs provided the matrix with self-diagnostic properties. A maximum electrical resistance change of approximately 21% was achieved under monotonic loading. The nanocomposites' fractional electrical resistance change decreased during compressive loading and increased during unloading. Electrical resistance change was found to return to zero value after every unloading cycle, indicating that no damage has been inflicted in the nanocomposites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cement based materials are the most commonly used construction materials because they are easy to handle and they are quite inexpensive. Nevertheless, they are susceptible to cracking which downgrades their mechanical behavior thus making the development of innovative ways to structural health monitor (SHM) a necessity [1]. Real-time monitoring of structures can fulfill the need for safer infrastructure reducing at the same time maintenance and repair costs by early diagnosis and treatment of durability problems. Current SHM technologies usually involve high-cost attached or embedded sensors that are application specific and provide information on particular locations of the structure. The implementation of these sensors is often limited by their size.

An innovative, low cost monitoring concept is that the material itself can be used to monitor the performance of an in-service structure, by measuring its electrical resistance. Cementitious materials, however, are nonconductive materials, therefore, the use of conductive reinforcement is necessary to provide the matrix with the capability to transfer electric current throughout its body. Graphene nanoplatelets (GnPs) demonstrate excellent mechanical and electrical properties which makes them appropriate material for the development of innovative cement based nanocomposites with stress/strain sensing capabilities.

The potential of using the GnPs as conductive reinforcement in cementitious materials was studied by Sedaghat et al [2]. The electrical resistivity of cement nanocomposites reinforced with 1, 5 and 10 vol% GnPs was studied. The results have shown that the resistivity of the cementitious matrix can be decreased with the implementation of GnPs. The possibility of using the cement/GnPs nanocomposites as sensors was demonstrated by Pang et al [3]. They investigated the sensing capability of mortar specimens with GnPs under both cyclic and monotonic compressive and tensile loadings. Results have shown that the graphene/cement nanocomposites could be used for sensing their structural integrity. Le

et al [4] studied the damage sensing capability of mortar samples with graphene nanoplatelets at high concentrations (i.e. 1.2 %, 2.4 %, 3.6 % and 4.8 % by volume of the material). Using the four-probe set-up, the electric potential across prismatic specimens with a known notch depth was measured and the results were compared with finite element simulations. No mechanical load was applied. It was demonstrated that as the GnPs amount exceeds a percolation threshold value (around 2.4 vol%), the electrical conductivity of the GnPs-infused mortar is insensitive to the moisture content, which makes it a reliable damage-sensing material for infrastructure applications. More, recently, Liu et al [5] investigated the compressive strength, electrical resistance, chloride penetration resistance and piezoresistive characteristics of mortar samples having different water-cement ratios and containing different amounts of GnPs and graphene oxide nanoplatelets (GONPs). According to the electrical resistance results, GnPs are a more preferable conductive filler compared to GONPs. It was found that to achieve low electrical resistance and an accurate piezoresistive response a quite large content of GnPs (from 6.4 up to 12.8% by weight of cement) should be used.

In the present work, the self-diagnostic characteristics of cement based nanocomposites, reinforced with exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets, under both monotonic and cyclic compressive tests were studied. According to the authors' previous work [6], the xGnPs lateral size plays an important role on their monitoring capability. Specifically, the fractional change in the electrical resistance is improved with increasing the xGnPs lateral dimension. To this end, exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets (xGnP) having a large lateral size of 25 μm at a low concentration of 0.15 wt% of cement were used. This concentration was found to be optimum as these particular samples demonstrated the lowest electrical resistivity [7]. One of the objectives of this research was to further study the piezoresistive characteristics of these cement-based nanocomposites and compare it with the reference sample results.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Type I ordinary Portland cement (CEM I 42,5 R) and Grade M graphene nanoplatelets supplied by XG sciences Inc, Michigan, were used. The xGnPs, according to the manufacturers' data sheet, had an average thickness of approximately 6–8 nm, a typical surface area of approximately 150 m^2/g and average particle diameter (lateral size) of 25 μm . To facilitate with the xGnPs dispersion, a superplasticizer based on polycarboxylate polymers, provided by Sika Hellas with the commercial name ViscoCrete® Ferro 1000 was used. This particular dispersant type was chosen because, based on the authors' previous research [8], it was found to be the most effective to homogeneously disperse the xGnPs in an aqueous solution for use with cement based materials.

2.2 xGnPs dispersion method

In order to take advantage of their excellent properties xGnPs need to be uniformly dispersed within the matrix. To achieve that, a simple method that combines the use of a dispersant agent and the application of ultrasonic energy was used in this study. Prior to their introduction to the matrix, the xGnPs were dispersed in an aqueous solution containing a third generation superplasticizer (dispersant agent) that is fully compatible with cementitious materials and it is typically used to improve their workability. Ultrasonic energy was applied to the suspensions by using a tip ultrasonic processor. One of the objectives was to achieve a homogeneous dispersion using a minimum amount of water. This could facilitate easy handling and adaptation of the xGnPs suspensions in the field. To achieve this, high concentrated xGnPs/aqueous suspensions were developed that contained only 9% of the mixing water and had a xGnPs concentration of 3.7 wt% of water. A constant superplasticizer to xGnPs weight ratio of 8.0 was used in all the dispersions. Ultrasonic energy was applied to the suspensions through a probe ultrasonicator that operated at 60 % of its power and at cycles of 0.5 s to prevent overheating of the suspensions. It should be noted that a higher ultrasonic power, compared to previous research [6], was chosen because according to visual observations the suspensions were more uniform.

Figure 1 shows three typical aqueous xGnPs suspensions with or without surfactant photographed immediately after mixing before the application of ultrasonic energy and the final solution combining the application of ultrasonic energy and treatment with the superplasticizer. Without the use of

superplasticizer (Figure 1a), due to their hydrophobic nature, the xGnPs are observed forming bundles at the top and at the bottom of the suspension. When a superplasticizer was used, the xGnPs started emerging in the aqueous solution being covered by the aqueous/dispersant solution indicating the good affinity between the xGnPs and the superplasticizer, Figure 1b. The water/superplasticizer solution (light brown solution) can be clearly seen at the bottom of the suspension. In both cases the xGnPs were agglomerated inside the solution demonstrating that the application of ultrasonic energy is required for the disentanglement of the xGnPs. After sonication, the suspension with the superplasticizer was uniform and no xGnP agglomerates were observed (Figure 1c).

Figure 1: xGnPs/aqueous suspensions (a) without superplasticizer and ultrasonic energy, (b) with superplasticizer and without ultrasonic energy and (c) with the implementation of a superplasticizer and the application of ultrasonic energy.

2.3 Nanocomposites casting

After dispersion, extra water was added to the xGnPs suspensions corresponding to a water to cement ratio of 0.3. The resulting mixture after hand stirring was mixed with the cement powder according to ASTM C305 using a standard mixer. After mixing, the cement paste nanocomposites were cast in prismatic 20×20×80 mm molds. Immediately after casting, to facilitate with the electrical resistance measurements, four stainless steel electrodes were embedded into the samples covering the entire cross-section of the specimens (Figure 2a). The distance between the outer and inner electrodes was 15 mm and the space between the inner electrodes was 30 mm. The specimens were demolded after one day and placed in water saturated with lime until the age of 28 days. Prior to testing, the samples were placed in an electrical heating oven with air circulation at a temperature of 80 ± 1 °C to dry for 72 h. At least three specimens were prepared for each case.

Figure 2: xGnP/cement nanocomposites (a) immediately after casting incorporating the four stainless steel electrodes covering the entire cross-section of the specimens and (b) after curing showing the specimen size and distances between the electrodes.

2.4 Test setup for piezoresistive properties measurement

The piezoresistive behavior of the produced nanocomposites was studied by measuring the electrical resistance of the nanocomposites under monotonic compression and loading-unloading compression tests. The electrical resistance was measured using the four wire method. An Agilent 34970a data acquisition system was used to record the four wire ohm measurements. The inner electrodes were used to measure the voltage and the outer electrodes to supply the direct current. The electrical resistance measurements were recorded every second during the mechanical tests. The monotonic compression tests were performed at a 300 kN Instron SATEC loading frame. The crosshead displacement rate was kept constant and equal to 0.5 mm/min. During testing time, crosshead displacement, mechanical force from the loading frame and electrical resistance from the multimeter were recorded. The cyclic compression tests were performed at a 10 kN MTS testing machine. The load was applied at a constant displacement rate of 0.3 mm/min so as each load-unload cycle would last approximately 120 s. A maximum load of 4 kN corresponding to a 10 MPa stress, which is in the elastic region of the material, was applied. The load and the electrical resistance were recorded during testing. The experimental test set up can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: (a) Experimental test set up and (b) close up view of the specimen.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Piezoresistive behavior under monotonic compression

To access the piezoresistive behaviour of the xGnPs reinforced cement based nanocomposites their electrical resistance was continuously measured using the four wire method while they were subjected to monotonic compression. The results are depicted in Figure 4. For comparison purposes, both the compressive stress (black squares) and the respective change in the electrical resistance (blue triangles) are plotted against the crosshead displacement. As expected, the electrical resistance change of the nanocomposites is inverse to the applied mechanical stress, i.e. the electrical resistance change is decreasing with the increase of the compressive mechanical force. This is because during loading the xGnPs are coming closer, their interparticle distances are decreasing facilitating electrical current flow which results to the observed reduction in the electrical resistance. At the beginning of loading (nanocomposites' elastic region) up until fracture (decrease in the mechanical stress) the fraction change in resistance is roughly linear. At the peak load, an increase in the electrical resistance change is noticed which coincides with specimen macro-cracking. This increase can be attributed to the breakage of conductive paths between the xGnPs due to cracking. After the peak load, due to crack opening, the electrical resistance change keeps increasing. From the beginning of loading up until the maximum load a 21% fractional change in the electrical resistance is observed. This electrical resistance change is much higher than what has been previously observed for similar nanocomposites [6]. This could be possibly due to the attainment of a more homogeneous distribution of the xGnPs inside the cementitious matrix, because of the application of higher ultrasonic power during xGnPs dispersion. The results are very encouraging and demonstrate the possibility of using the xGnPs for monitoring purposes in cementitious materials.

Figure 4: Monotonic compressive stress and fractional electrical resistance change over crosshead displacement of the xGnPs/cement based nanocomposites.

3.2 Piezoresistive behavior under cyclic compression

The xGnPs nanocomposites were also subjected to several loading-unloading cycles under compression within the elastic region of the material. Taking into account that the compressive strength of the nanocomposites is approximately 80 MPa, the applied maximum stress of 10 MPa during loading is around 12% of its compressive strength. The reference (without reinforcement) samples, were also subjected to the same experimental protocol. The same maximum stress was applied, which corresponds to 20% of the material's compressive strength ($\sigma_{max} = 50$ MPa [6]) and lies also within the elastic region of the material. The results are shown in Figure 5. The applied compressive strength (black squares) and fractional change in resistance for both, reference samples (Figure 5a, red squares) and nanocomposites (Figure 5b, blue stars) are depicted against experimental time. In both cases, no mechanical degradation of the material (residual deformation) due to application of the mechanical stress for the investigated cycles was observed. In the case of reference cement paste, the electrical resistance during the first loading cycle is observed to decrease, however, after that it starts oscillating at an unpredicted manner. It is clear that the reference material cannot be used as a piezoresistive sensor. On the contrary, the nanocomposites demonstrate an excellent piezoresistive behavior. Their electrical resistance is changing inversely proportional to the applied stress, which indicates that they can be used as sensors. Furthermore, in every cycle the fractional change in resistance is returning to its initial value, indicating that no damage occurred in the control volume of the nanocomposites. The results have shown that the implementation of a conductive reinforcement is necessary to provide the matrix with the capability to change its resistance according to the applied stress.

Figure 5: Cyclic compressive stress and fractional electrical resistance change over testing time of (a) reference cement paste and (b) xGnPs/cement based nanocomposites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The self-diagnostic characteristics under both monotonic and cyclic compression of cement based nanocomposites reinforced with exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets were investigated in this study. The results can be summarized as following:

- The fractional resistance change of the nanocomposites was found to be inversely proportional to the applied stress. This could be attributed to the reduction of the xGNPs interparticle distances that occurs during loading.
- The reference samples results under several loading-unloading compressive cycles have shown that plain cement paste does not demonstrate stable piezoresistive properties and therefore cannot be used for self-monitoring purposes. The use of a conductive reinforcement is necessary to provide the material with the capability to change its electrical properties according to the applied stress.
- The xGNP/cement nanocomposites demonstrate a linear change of the electrical resistance during compressive loading. During cyclic compression at the elastic region, the electrical resistance changes according to the applied stress and upon specimen unloading is returning to zero value, indicating that no damage has been inflicted.

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